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Kinetic rates for calcination and carbonation of Vernasca raw meal

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Short description

This Deliverable reports the results obtained from the tests carried out with samples of Vernasca raw meal (and derived solids) supplied by Buzzi. The goal of the tests is to quantify the kinetic rates of calcination and carbonation under conditions as close as possible to those expected in the Cleanker Calcium Looping pilot, which will use Vernasca raw meal as solid feed. This task has been accomplished taking into account the different behaviour of the three main components of Vernasca raw meal in the calcium looping system: the fraction of CaCO_3 -rich particles (limestone), the fraction of Ca-Si particles (the marl) and the fraction of inert materials that do not participate in the reactions with CO_2 (but that may sequester part of the free CaO to form stable compounds). Vernasca is mainly a binary mixture 0.72 wt/wt of a marl (Marine) and 0.28 wt/wt of a limestone (Calccare).

Two thermogravimetric set ups have been used to determine the evolution with time of both carbonation and calcination conversions of Vernasca at different temperatures and partial pressure of CO_2 , as well as the belite formation and the decay constants that describe the drop in the maximum carrying capacity of the sorbent with the number of calcination-carbonation cycles. The decay constants determined for the Vernasca limestone fraction (Calccare) ($k = 0.57$ and $X_r = 0.060$) are shown to be comparable to typical values reported for other standard limestones. However, the raw meal has yielded much more complex behaviour with the operating conditions (i.e. the CO_2 carrying capacities was shown to be especially sensitive to calcination times and temperatures) due to belite formation (and other silicates) detectable by XRD analyses. Thus, the belite formation rate was investigated independently and fitted to the Jander's kinetic model, resulting in a calculated activation energy of 336 kJ/mol, which is similar to that reported in the literature for CaO-SiO₂ mixtures (i.e. no raw meals) at higher temperatures (between 1000 and 1500 °C).

On the other hand, the activation energy derived for the calcination reaction, obtained from TG experiments with Vernasca solids (85 kJ/mol) has also been found to be consistent with some previously published data. However, the pre-exponential factors (and hence the overall reactions rates) are subjected to great uncertainty if only the TG measurements are used as a basis to derive kinetic parameters, as there are signs indicating substantial undesired effects in the TG reaction environment compared with the entrained bed results. Regarding the carbonation kinetics, the parameters obtained are an activation energy of 26 kJ/mol and a pre-exponential factor of 4.51 s⁻¹.

A drop tube furnace has been commissioned to simulate the reaction environments of the solids as close as possible to those expected in the pilot and to generate calcined solid samples of Vernasca and other raw meals in time scales of 1-5 seconds, thereby decoupling the calcination reaction from the belite formation reactions. Although results from this facility were not originally planned for this deliverable, it is important to note here that the initial results have confirmed the high activity and CO_2 carrying capacity of the calcined raw meal of Vernasca when calcination is sufficiently fast to minimise reactions of CaO with other solid species in the marl component of the raw meal. From these preliminary tests, it was also found that

calcination kinetics can be an order of magnitude faster than the kinetics predicted by the simplified kinetic correlations derived for this reaction in the TGA. Therefore, a re-adjustment of the kinetic parameters has been carried out after the experimental campaign in this reactor, to tune the calcination model to the observed experimental results. As planned in the workplan for WP5, future experimental and modelling work with other materials and raw meals, at relevant calcination and carbonation conditions and reaction times, should improve the understanding of the results described in this deliverable. However, the information reported here for Vernasca raw meal should be taken into account in the design and operation strategies of the Cleanker pilot.

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SCOPE AND INTRODUCTION

This Deliverable reports the results obtained from the tests carried out with samples of Vernasca raw meal (and derived solids) supplied by Buzzi. The experiments have been focused on quantifying under realistic conditions the kinetic rates of the main reactions that take place in the Cleankер pilot when Vernasca raw meal is used as solid feed. This task has been carried out taking into account the different behaviour of the three main components present in Vernasca raw meal in the calcium looping system: the fraction of CaCO_3 -rich particles (limestone), the fraction of Ca-Si particles (marl) and the fraction of inert materials that do not participate in the reactions with CO_2 (but that may react with free CaO to form stable compounds). Two thermogravimetric set-ups have been used to determine the evolution with time of both carbonation and calcination conversions of Vernasca raw meal at different temperatures and partial pressure of CO_2 . Moreover, previous studies with other raw meals (CEMCAP, D12.2) showed that Ca_2SiO_4 (belite) can be formed under typical operation conditions of calcium looping. Belite is not able to react with CO_2 and, therefore, some of the initial CaO is deactivated for carbonation reaction. The kinetics of belite formation from both CaCO_3 and CaO were studied and subsequently implemented in a tuned calcination model able to describe the experimental results and predict the behaviour of the sorbent.

A drop tube furnace has been commissioned to simulate reaction environments close to those expected in the pilot plant and to generate calcined solid samples of Vernasca and other raw meals in time scales of 1-5 seconds, thereby decoupling the calcination reaction from the belite formation. There is a high dispersion in the literature (Martinez et al., 2012; Borgwardt, 1985) on the activation energies calculated for the calcination of CaCO_3 (between 90 kJ/mol and 200 kJ/mol) due to the use of different setups and a wide range of particle sizes. As a result, the estimation of calcination reaction rates are still subjected to great uncertainty, especially if they are obtained only from TGA, since significant undesired effects could be present in the TG reaction environment. Therefore, the experimental results obtained from the drop tube will be used for the validation of the models derived from the TGA tests.

In section 1 of this Deliverable, the results related to the characterization of the Vernasca raw meal and its derived solids are described. Chemical compositions measured by X-ray Fluorescence and X-ray Diffraction and particle size distributions obtained by laser diffraction are provided. In section 2, the experimental set-ups and experimental procedures used for the kinetic studies are described. Section 3 includes the experimental results obtained in the TGA and section 4 presents the kinetic models and parameters derived from the experimental results in the TGA. Finally the experimental results obtained in the drop tube and their preliminary analyses are presented in Section 5.

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1. PHYSICAL AND CHEMICAL CHARACTERISATION OF VERNASCA RAW MEAL AND ITS DERIVED SOLIDS

Several facilities available at CSIC has been used to characterize the solid materials, such as a SRF 3000 Bruker equipment for XRF and a Bruker D8 Advance for XRD to determine the chemical composition, and a Beckman-Coulter LS 13320 laser diffraction particle size analyser to measure the particle size distribution.

Samples of Vernasca raw meal and the individual raw components were supplied by Buzzi to CSIC. Vernasca raw meal, which is a mixture of a limestone (Calcare) and a marl (Marine), was received in powder form as used in the industrial plant. However, the samples of both Calcare and Marine initially contained large particles (with particle size of up several cms), so they were milled and sieved at CSIC to minimize the effect of the particle size on the reaction studies.

The chemical compositions of Vernasca, and its individual raw components measured by X-ray Fluorescence are shown in Table 1. The composition of an additional raw meal (called Bilbao in this Deliverable) obtained from the Heidelberg's plant located in Arrigorriaga (Spain) and used as a reference material, is also included in Table 1.1.

Table 1.1. Chemical compositions of Vernasca and Bilbao raw meals, Calcare (limestone) and Marine (marl) measured by XRF.

Oxide (wt.%)	Vernasca	Calcare	Marine	Bilbao
Na ₂ O	-	-	0.24	-
MgO	1.26	1.87	1.23	0.65
Al ₂ O ₃	3.56	0.22	4.86	4.09
SiO ₂	15.21	0.37	21.03	13.39
P ₂ O ₅	0.1	-	0.05	-
K ₂ O	0.57	0.05	0.97	0.89
CaO	41.50	53.26	37.09	42.72
TiO ₂	0.16	-	0.22	0.18
Fe ₂ O ₃	2.13	0.06	1.65	1.94
SO ₃	0.30	0.10	0.45	1.04
MnO	0.08	-	0.08	-
SrO	0.08	0.02	0.10	-
ZrO ₂	0.02	-	0.02	-
LOI*	35.26	44.06	32.17	35.01

*Loss On Ignition

As can be seen, the chemical compositions of Vernasca and Bilbao raw meals are similar. Both contain CaO and SiO₂ of around 42 and 14 wt.%, respectively. On the other hand, Calcare is a quite pure limestone whose main impurity is MgCO₃, and Marine is a marl with CaO and SiO₂ contents of 37 and 21 wt.%, respectively. From the results presented in Table 1.1, it can be estimated that Vernasca is a binary mixture composed of 72 wt.% of Marine and 28 wt.% of Calcare.

Figure 1.1 shows the X-ray Diffraction (XRD) analyses of Vernasca and Bilbao raw meals. Diffraction data were collected by step scanning using a step size of 0.02° , a scan step of 4 s and a scan range between 5° and 60° . As can be seen, both spectra are very similar and the highest intensities correspond to CaCO_3 and SiO_2 compounds.

Figure 1.1. XRD spectra of Vernasca and Bilbao raw meals.

As reported by Taylor (1997), between 500 and 1250°C several calcium silicates can be present in Ca-Si compounds, such as Ca_2SiO_4 (belite), Ca_3SiO_5 (alite) or $\text{Ca}_3\text{Si}_2\text{O}_7$ (rankinite). Samples of Vernasca and Marine were calcined in a TGA in the presence of air at 900°C during 30 minutes (i.e., using a similar temperature to a CaL system) in order to produce enough mass of sample for XRD analysis in order to identify Ca-Si phases formed during the calcination. Both overlapped spectra are shown in Figure 1.2. As can be seen, Ca_2SiO_4 (Belite) is the main calcium silicate formed (apart from very small amounts of alite). For this reason, the formation of belite during typical conditions of calcium looping has been studied in detail, as the main factor of raw meal deactivation during the carbonation/calcination operation.

Figure 1.2. XRD spectra of calcined Vernasca and Marine. Calcination conditions: T_{calc} : 900°C , atmosphere: air, t_{calc} : 30 min.

As the particle size is an important parameter in solid-solid and gas-solid reactions, the particle size distributions (PSD) of the solid samples were determined. In Figure 1.3, the particle size distributions of Vernasca and Bilbao raw meals are compared.

Figure 1.3. Particle Size distributions of Vernasca (left) and Bilbao (right) raw meals.

As can be seen in the case of Vernasca raw meal, different volumetric fractions are observed clearly separated for certain particle size ranges as corresponds to a mixture of separate compounds. However, Bilbao raw meal exhibits a much more homogeneous particle size distribution, characteristic of a single compound. Moreover, the Sauter diameter as well as the dp_{50} are 6 and 9 μm , respectively, for both raw meals. Thus, it is not expected different behaviour between both raw meals due to the particle size. Very similar PSDs for the individual components of Vernasca raw meal (Calcare and Marine) were obtained once they were milled and sieved (see Figure 1.4).

Figure 1.4. Particle Size distributions of Vernasca components: Calcare (left) and Marine (right).

2. EXPERIMENTAL FACILITIES USED FOR VERNASCA KINETIC STUDIES

2.1 Thermogravimetric analysers and experimental procedures

The kinetic studies carried out with Vernasca raw meal were performed in two thermogravimetric analysers at CSIC. In the following subsections the main features of this equipment as well as the experimental procedures are described.

2.1.1 TA-Q5000 IR analyser

The Q5000 IR (TA Instruments) analyser is a commercial TGA whose main features are: thermally control head balance, an infrared oven that can achieve programmable heating rates up to 500 °C/min and a base line dynamic drift less than 10 µg (after correction with blank test). These characteristics make this TGA suitable for non-isothermal tests and was used for the kinetic study of belite formation from CaCO₃ (i.e., before calcination) as described below .

2.1.2 In-house thermogravimetric analyser

In the in-house TGA, the sample is placed in a platinum basket suspended inside a mullite tube of $2.54 \cdot 10^{-2}$ m O.D. The mullite tube is surrounded by two electrical ovens controlled independently by means of two temperature controllers. The oven placed at the bottom was used as a gas pre-heater whereas the upper oven was used to set the operating temperature. The sample temperature is measured by a thermocouple located 5 mm below the platinum basket. The reactant gases are fed into the bottom of the tube and the flowrates are regulated by mass-flow controllers. The sample weight, temperatures and gas flowrates are continuously recorded in a computer during the tests.

This experimental setup allows carrying out kinetic studies under isothermal conditions. From these kinetic studies, it is possible to deduce the type of reaction from the conversion vs time plots (in contrast to non-isothermal tests, where the plots always follow sinusoidal-type curves). Moreover, the reaction rate equation has an analytical solution for the main mechanisms known. Therefore, isothermal studies were carried out every time was possible. The CO₂ carrying capacity, the belite formation from CaO and the calcination tests were carried out in this TGA.

2.1.3 Experimental procedures used for Vernasca kinetic studies

Four kind of experiments were carried out in the TG analysers as described in this section: a) the determination of the CO₂ carrying capacity of the sorbent and its evolution with the number of cycles, b) the formation of belite considering that it is formed by the reaction of SiO₂ with CaCO₃ and CaO, c) calcination tests and d) carbonation tests.

a. CO₂ carrying capacity tests

These tests were carried out with initial sample weights of around 10 mg. This amount of sample should compensate the sintering effect over the external CaO surface (Alonso et al., 2014). This sintering effect is very small in the first carbonation/calcination cycle over sample weights of between 2 and 10 mg (i.e. differences in conversions lower than 0.02). However, the effect is cumulative in the long term. Therefore, large sample weights are required at the expense of working under diffusional resistance regime that do affect to the determination of the CO₂ carrying capacity. Each test starts by heating-up the sample from room temperature up to 650 °C in an atmosphere of 10 vol% CO₂ in air. Under these conditions, the calcination of the samples is avoided and the buoyant force can be determined at this temperature. Once both the temperature and weight are stable, the atmosphere is switched to air and the sample is heated-up to 900 °C. This temperature is maintaining for 10 minutes to accomplish the calcination of the sample. From that moment onwards, the sample is cooled down to 650 °C in air. Once the temperature and weight stabilise, the carbonation step is initiated by feeding gas at 0.06 m/s containing 10 vol% CO₂ in air. The carbonation time is extended for 10 min in order to achieve the maximum CO₂ carrying capacity, X_N , in each cycle.

b. Belite reaction from CaCO₃ tests

Belite can be formed from the reaction between SiO₂ and CaCO₃ according to [2.1]. This reaction can take place during the heating up of the particles in the calciner before calcination or in other devices where CaCO₃ is present at high temperature.

These reaction tests were carried out with initial sample weights of around 2 mg at three different heating rates (5, 10 and 30 °C/min) up to 900 °C in 100 vol.% CO₂. A gas velocity of 0.07 m/s at 900 °C was used for these tests. Additional experiments with final temperatures of 800 °C and 850 °C at a constant heating rate of 30 °C/min were also carried out. Moreover, blank tests with an empty pan were performed in order to determine the buoyant force. Thus, the sample is heated up to the final temperature. Once the maximum temperature is achieved, the conditions are maintained for 30 min. Following this experimental procedure, the calcination of CaCO₃ is avoided due to equilibrium restrictions. The weight loss observed is assumed to be due to the reaction between CaCO₃ and SiO₂ to form Ca₂SiO₄. Thus, the conversion of CaCO₃ to belite (X_{Bb}) can be calculated directly from the measurement of the weight loss.

c. Belite reaction from CaO tests

Belite can also be formed from CaO according to reaction [2.2], in which the weight of the solid remains stable during the calcination:

Thus, the conversion of CaO to belite (X_{Ba}) has been estimated indirectly assuming that the decrease in the CO₂ carrying capacity of the samples is caused exclusively by the formation of belite. Then, the total conversion of CaO to belite (X_B) can be calculated as:

$$X_B = 1 - \frac{X_{carb}}{X_{max}} \quad [2.3]$$

where X_{carb} is the carbonation conversion measured at the end of the carbonation period and X_{max} is the carbonation that should be achieved if no belite is formed. During the heating up of the particles in these experiments, a small fraction of belite can be formed from CaCO₃ according to reaction 2.1 (X_{Bb}). This is estimated by using the model described in section 4, and the belite formed from CaO (X_{Ba}) (reaction 2.2) can be then calculated from the difference between the total conversion to belite (X_B) and X_{Bb} .

For these tests, initial sample weights of around 2 mg were used. The sample is heated up to 650 °C in 10 vol.% of CO₂ in air to determine the buoyant force. Then, the sample is heated until the calcination temperature is reached in the presence of 100 vol% CO₂. Different calcination temperatures between 840 °C and 920 °C were tested. To initiate the calcination stage the gas feed is switched from 100 vol.% CO₂ to air. The calcination temperature is then maintained during a period of time ranging from 30 seconds to 200 minutes. Afterwards, the samples are cooled down to 650 °C in the presence of air and subsequently carbonated at this temperature in 10 %vol.CO₂ in air for 5 min. The carbonation conversion (X_{carb}) is calculated at the end of this period. To determine carbonation conversion when no belite is formed (X_{max}), several tests were carried out following the procedure described above but performing the calcination stage at 800 °C for 1 min.

d. Calcination kinetics tests

In these tests, the initial sample weights were around 2 mg. The sample was heated in 100 vol.% CO₂ until a temperatures below 900 °C was achieved in order to avoid the calcination of CaCO₃ during the heating up. Once the maximum temperature was achieved, atmosphere calcination composition was adjusted to start the calcination step. Calcination temperatures between 805 and 895 °C were tested. The effect of the partial pressure of CO₂ on the calcination kinetics was also evaluated. For this reason, several tests at 895 °C with molar fractions of CO₂ in the feed ranging between 0 and 0.8 were carried out. The conversion of CaCO₃ to CaO can be calculated directly from the weight loss measured during the tests taking into account that the molar fraction of CaCO₃ (mol of CaCO₃/mol of total CaO) is typically lower than 1 at the beginning of the calcination stage due to the formation of belite (reaction [2.1]) during the heating period. Therefore, the calcination conversion, X_{calc} , can be estimated from the difference between the total loss of weight measured in TGA and the estimated loss of weight (using the fitted model) due to belite formation from CaCO₃ (reaction 2.1). Blank tests were also performed by using samples of quartz of similar weights for accounting the buoyancy effects.

e. Carbonation kinetics tests

In this type of tests the initial sample weights of around 2 mg were used. Each sample was initially calcined at 800 °C in air during 5 minutes (the heating period until 800 °C is carried out in 100 vol.% CO₂). After calcination, the sample was cooled down to the carbonation temperature in air atmosphere. Carbonation temperatures between 615 and 700 °C were tested under a molar fraction of CO₂ of 0.1. Moreover, in order to study the effect of CO₂ concentration, additional tests at 655 °C were carried by varying the CO₂ molar fraction between 0.1 and 1.

Following the procedures described above, the kinetic reaction rates of belite formation, CaCO₃ calcination and CaO carbonation reactions of Vernasca were measured and fitted to simplified kinetic models. The experimental results are presented in section 3, whereas the modelling work is presented in section 4.

2.2 Drop tube furnace

CSIC has built and commissioned a drop tube reactor to test fast gas-solid reaction kinetics relevant for the CLEANKER project. This facility allows obtaining experimental information on reaction kinetics and other reaction phenomena in very short gas/solid contact times (i.e., lower than 5 seconds), hardly approachable for other experimental setups (such as thermogravimetric analysers). The operation of the drop tube has been carried out with very low loadings of solids to allow differential conditions with respect to the gas. This means that only modest changes in the concentration of the gas are allowed during the tests, so that all particles ideally experienced a similar controlled and measured reaction environment along the reactor. The drop tube is 6.5 m long with an internal diameter of 80 mm. The reaction zone has a length of 5.48 m. Three heating elements with an individual capacity of 3.5 kW_e (and connected to independent controllers) are installed along the tube to counteract the heat loss. Moreover, the reactor is surrounded by a 200 mm width layer of glass wool.

Figure 2.1. Drop tube set-up (left) and solids feeding system (right).

As can be seen in Figure 2.1, the solids and the carrier gas are injected at the top of the drop tube (i.e. at 5.48 m from the outlet) and move downwards together with the gas flow. The purpose-built solids feeding system comprises a cylindrical perex reservoir (0.03 m ID) containing a bed of the solids to be fed into the system. A flow of air of about 0.5 m³/h coming from a compressor at 5 bar and regulated by a mass-flow controller is injected into the reservoir acting as solids carrier. A thinner metallic tube is inserted in the bed of solids that is used to drain the particles as the tip of the pipe moves downwards. This movement is achieved by connecting the metallic tube to an electric motor equipped with a speed variator to control the rotation motion (see Figure 2.1 right) of a shaft connected to the motor. In a typical experiment, a batch of

around 150 g of solids is fed into the reactor. The flowrate of solids is proportional to the vertical displacement velocity of the drainage tube. In addition, the mass of solids in the reservoir is measured before and after each experiment to validate the actual mass flow rate. The maximum rate of displacement is 5.6 m/h, which allows solids flow rates of up to 8 kg/h. Moreover, a vibration device attached to the cylinder ensures a uniform discharge of the solids. Both solids and gas carrier are preheated up to 500 °C before they enter into the reactor.

Different gas compositions can be tested by mixing air, CO₂ and water vapour (when relevant), which are heated up by a Kanthal® electric gas preheater with an electric power of 3.5 kW_e able to operate at a maximum temperature of 1100 °C. Air is supplied by a blower with a maximum capacity of 90 m³/h, while the CO₂ comes from bottles. Air and CO₂ flow rates are regulated using mass flow controllers. The water vapour is provided by a steam generator that can supply a maximum continuous flow of 1.8 kg H₂O/h. This stream is injected into the reactor when necessary by the secondary gas injection (see Figure 2.1).

There are eleven measurement points for gas analysis located each 500 mm along the reaction zone, which makes possible to evaluate the gas composition at different reaction lengths. Two analysers (ABB EL3020, ABB AO2000) and two CO₂Meter® sensors (GC-0016 COZIR) were used for this purpose. Each gas sampling line is equipped with a particulate filter to protect the analysers from the sorbent particles. When working with water vapour, a heating element and a drier system are also installed in order to remove the moisture from the gas sent to the analyser. Each point is also equipped with thermocouples to measure the temperature profile in the reactor. All the electric signals from the thermocouples, gas analysers and mass flow controllers are collected in a computer using a data logger. At the reactor exit the hot gas and solids are mixed with air at ambient temperature in order to quench the reaction. Moreover, a fraction of the particles leaving the reactor are collected using a solids sampling device for a subsequent analysis and characterization.

3. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS FROM TG EXPERIMENTS

3.1 CO₂ carrying capacity of Vernasca raw meal

The CO₂ carrying capacity of a calcined material is defined as the molar conversion to CaCO₃ in relation to the total moles of CaO initially present in the material ($X = \text{moles CaCO}_3 / \text{moles CaO}$). From a practical point of view, the maximum CO₂ carrying capacity has been calculated as the molar conversion achieved at the end of the carbonation period in the TG. Several CO₂ carrying capacity tests were carried out with calcined Vernasca raw meal following the experimental procedure explained in section 2.1.3.a. As example, Figure 3.1 left shows the evolution of the carbonation conversion of this material. For comparison purposes, the results obtained with calcined Bilbao raw meal (with similar chemical composition) and with a synthetic mixture (SRM) composed of

CaCO₃ (86 w%) and SiO₂ nanoparticles (14 w%) are also included in this figure. As can be seen, the sorbent conversion increases rapidly and stabilizes after 20 seconds.

Figure 3.1. Evolution of the CO₂ carrying capacity during after the first calcination of Vernasca and Bilbao raw meals and synthetic mixture (SRM) after a calcination carried out at 900 °C during 1 minute in air (left). Evolution of the maximum CO₂ carrying capacity with the number of carbonation/calcination cycles for Vernasca ($t_{\text{calcination}}=1$ and 10 min) and for a reference limestone, LS ($t_{\text{calcination}}=10$ min) (right).

Both calcined Vernasca and SRM achieved a similar maximum value of around 0.6. In contrast, the maximum CO₂ carrying capacity obtained with calcined Bilbao raw meal was significantly lower (around 0.15). The higher level of aggregation between Ca and Si compounds in Bilbao raw meal greatly reduces the CO₂ carrying capacity, because this type of material is prone to form belite during the calcination (Alonso et al., 2017).

Despite, Vernasca shows a reasonably high value of maximum CO₂ carrying capacity in the first cycle, a typical deactivation of Ca-based sorbents is observed as the number of calcination/carbonation cycles increases (see Figure 3.1 right). The decay in the carrying capacity with the number of cycles (X_N) of the CaO from limestones can be described by the equation obtained by Grasa and Abanades (Grasa and Abanades, 2006):

$$X_N = \frac{1}{\left(\frac{1}{(1-X_r)} + kN\right)} + X_r \quad [3.1]$$

where k is the decay constant and X_r is the residual conversion. Both parameters take average values of 0.52 and 0.075 for a wide range of Ca-derived sorbents.

As can be seen in Figure 3.1 right, the operating conditions chosen for the calcination step decisively affect the evolution of CO₂ carrying capacities during cycling. Lower values were systematically observed for calcined Vernasca when the calcination

time is increased from 1 to 10 minutes (around 30 % lower during the first 5 cycles). The solid black line in Figure 3.1 right represents the expected evolution sorbent conversion during cycling for a reference sorbent ($k=0.52$ and $X_r=0.075$). When the calcination of Vernasca raw meal is carried out at 900 °C during 1 minute in air, the experimental data can be fitted to Equation 3.1 by assuming that only a 0.75 molar fraction of CaO is available to react with CO₂ (i.e. with the same performance of a sorbent derived from a limestone). However, in the case of calcining at 900 °C for 10 minutes, the fitting of the experimental results to Equation 3.1 indicates that only a 0.5 molar fraction of CaO is available for carbonation. These results indicate that the CaO availability (due to the belite formation) is greatly influenced by the calcination time.

In view of these results and from the experience with other raw meals tested in the CEMCAP project (see Alonso et al 2017), it was decided to study separately the performance of the two main components in Vernasca’s raw meal (i.e., the limestone-type fraction Calcarea and the marl-type fraction Marine). Figure 3.2 left shows the evolution with time of the CaO molar conversion to CaCO₃ for Calcarea during the first 5 cycles. In Figure 3.2 right, the evolution of the CO₂ carrying capacity with the number of calcination-carbonation cycles, X_N vs N, is represented. As can be seen, the behaviour of Calcarea is similar to that typically found in limestones. In fact, the decay in the CO₂ carrying capacity of Calcarea in the long term can be accurately described by the equation [3.1] with values of $k=0.57$ and $X_r=0.06$.

Figure 3.2. Evolution of the carbonation conversion of Calcarea limestone-type fraction during the first 5 cycles under the standard CO₂ carrying capacity test (left). Decay of the maximum carrying capacity with the number of cycles of Calcarea limestone-type fraction.

Figure 3.3 shows the evolution with time of the CaO molar conversion to CaCO₃ for Marine during the first 5 cycles and the evolution of the CO₂ carrying capacity with the number of calcination-carbonation cycles. In this case, the calcination period has been reduced from 10 to only 1 min. Despite that, the CaO molar conversion to CaCO₃ in Marine for each cycle is significantly lower than that observed in Calcare. A molar conversion below 0.15 is obtained in cycle 5, whereas about 0.30 is achieved with Calcare in the same cycle. The CO₂ carrying capacity decay curve is described by equation [3.1] with values of $k=1.45$ and $X_r=0.044$, which are about 2.5 times higher and 27% lower, respectively, compared to the fitting parameters calculated for Calcare.

Figure 3.3. Evolution of the carbonation conversion of Marine (marl) during the first 5 cycles (t calcination of 1 min) (left). Decay of the maximum carrying capacity with the number of cycles of Marine (right).

3.2 Extent of Belite formation during the calcination of Vernasca

The formation of belite (Ca₂SiO₄) in the calciner of a Calcium Looping system could be in principle considered as a desirable reaction, as it is one of reactions required for clinker production. However, this reaction may strongly undermine the operation of the carbonator reactor since part of the CaO could form a stable Ca-Si compound thereby reducing the amount of active CaO.

In view of the results described in section 3.1. and the results reported by Alonso et al (2017) for other raw meals, it can be assumed that the fraction of active CaO determines in general the sorbent performance as it presents a similar behaviour regardless of the origin of the material (i.e. if CaO comes from a limestone or from other CaO-based material). Thus, the differences in the performance of different raw meals would be caused mainly by the CaO/CaCO₃ conversions to belite. The methodology explained in Section 2 to characterize the rates of Belite formation has been applied to the Vernasca raw meal. The objective is to estimate the evolution of

the molar conversion of CaO to Ca_2SiO_4 , X_B , with time under different reaction conditions. Thus, the fraction of active CaO present in the material, and therefore, its performance, should be given by the difference between the initial fraction of CaO and X_B .

As explained in section 2 in a calcium looping system, belite can be formed from CaO (i.e., after calcination), described by equation [2.2], or from CaCO_3 described by reaction [2.1]. The total conversion to belite ($X_B = X_{Ba} + X_{Bb}$), including the separate calculation of CaO and CaCO_3 conversions, X_{Bb} and X_{Ba} , respectively, can be obtained following the procedure detailed in Section 2.

Figure 3.4 shows the evolution with time of CaCO_3 conversion to belite (X_{Bb}) for Vernasca raw meal at temperatures below $900\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ in pure CO_2 atmosphere using three heating rates (i.e., 5, 10 and $30\text{ }^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$). As can be seen in Figure 3.4. left, the heating rates do not affect the formation of belite since a similar X_{Bb} is achieved (around 0.24) once $900\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ is reached. On the other hand, higher temperatures favoured belite formation from CaCO_3 as shown in Figure 3.3 right. At $800\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, a maximum X_{Bb} of about 0.15 was achieved after 25 min. During the same period of time, a value of around 0.25 was reached at a temperature of $900\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ (maintaining the same heating rate of $30\text{ }^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$).

Figure 3.4. Conversion of CaCO_3 to belite before calcination (with heating rates of 5, 10, $30\text{ }^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$ and final temperature of $900\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$) (left) Evolution of CaCO_3 conversion to belite before calcination at different final temperatures and a heating rate of $30\text{ }^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$ (right).

It must be noted that the time scales used in these experiments may be in principle too long to be relevant for the CaL process. However residence times of several minutes can be considered realistic to represent the situation of particles located in dead zones of the calciner or other devices (i.e. hoppers, feeding systems, etc) at high temperatures and/or of those subjected to multiple carbonation/calcination cycles. These experimental data covering large periods of time will be valuable to fit more

robust kinetic models (see section 5) that could describe more narrow operating windows for the reactors and devices of the CLEANKER pilot plant. Moreover, the determination of CaCO_3 conversion to belite vs time is essential to interpret the results obtained from the TG device as there is an unavoidable X_{Bb} during the heating of the sample up to the calcination temperature (between 3 and 15 minutes are required depending on the heating rate and final temperature).

Once the calcination is complete, belite can be formed from the CaO present in the sample. As indicated in section 2, this reaction path has been studied by means of isothermal experiments. The conversion of CaO to belite (X_{Ba}) has been calculated from the loss of activity of the sorbent, which allows the total belite conversion (X_B) to be calculated. The effect of the calcination temperature on the conversion of CaO to belite is represented in Figure 3.5.

Figure 3.5. Effect of the calcination temperature on the conversion of CaO to Belite (after calcination) at calcination temperatures between 840 °C and 920 °C.

The experimental results presented in this figure indicate a great effect of the calcination temperature on the formation of belite from CaO (suggesting a high activation energy, as discussed in section 4). Almost 50 minutes are required to achieve CaO conversions to belite higher than 0.3 when the calcination is carried out at 840 °C. However, at a calcination temperature of 920 °C values of X_{Ba} higher than 0.5 are reached in barely 10 min.

3.3 Calcination experiments with Vernasca in TG

The effect of the temperature and the CO_2 content in the atmosphere on the calcination of Vernasca raw meal was also evaluated. The experimental results obtained in TG following the experimental procedure described in Section 2.1 are represented in Figure 3.6. As expected, higher calcination temperatures favoured the calcination of

CaCO₃. A stronger effect of the CO₂ concentration on the calcination reaction rate was also observed. At temperatures around 900 °C, almost the complete calcination of CaCO₃ can be achieved in air in 30 s. However, the calcination carried out with 80 vol.% of CO₂ in the gas phase was found to be much slower, giving rise to calcination conversions below 0.20 after 200 s of operation.

Figure 3.6. Effect of the temperature on the calcination conversion vs time of Vernasca (left) Effect of the CO₂ concentration in the gas phase on the calcination rate (calcination temperature of 895 °C) (right).

Unfortunately, it is not possible in the TG apparatus to obtain similar X_{calc} vs time curves for temperatures above 900°C in pure CO₂ due to the competition of the belite formation and calcination rates under non-isothermal conditions. It must be highlighted that the calcination times obtained in general in the TGA were significantly longer than those reported in the literature for limestones with similar particle sizes in suspension reactors (Bordwardt, 1985) and those reported in the drop tube reactor (section 5). These discrepancies may be due to certain diffusional resistances in the TGA, which would limit the measure of reliable kinetics of very fast reaction rates as happens with the calcination of CaCO₃. The results obtained under differential conditions in the drop tube reactor (explained in section 5) should allow for an accurate fitting of the kinetic parameters of the model facilitating the scalability of the results.

3.4 Carbonation experiments with Vernasca in TG

The carbonation rate of Vernasca raw meal was also studied in TGA for different temperatures and CO₂ concentrations in the gas phase. Figure 3.7 shows the experimental results obtained following the procedure described in Section 2.1.

Figure 3.7. Carbonation conversion of CaO from Vernasca. Effect of carbonation temperature at a CO₂ molar fraction of 0.1 (left). Effect of CO₂ concentration at a carbonation temperature of 655 °C (right).

Very similar carbonation rates were observed (during the period of fast carbonation) at temperatures between 615 and 700 °C. This behaviour has also been observed during the carbonation of CaO derived from limestones (Grasa et al. 2008). On the other hand, the CO₂ concentration in the gas phase greatly affects the carbonation rate of Vernasca. Higher contents of CO₂ accelerate the carbonation conversion. The maximum carbonation conversion ($X=0.6$) operating with 10 vol% CO₂ is achieved after 26 s. When the carbonation is accomplished with 80 vol.% CO₂ the reaction rate is 4 times faster, as can be seen in Figure 3.7 left. When the carbonation is carried out with pure CO₂, the reaction rate and the conversion to CaCO₃ observed for Vernasca is significantly slower due to some pore blockage, as occurs with CaO from limestones (Grasa et al. 2008).

4. RECOMMENDED SIMPLIFIED KINETIC MODELS FOR VERNASCA DERIVED MATERIALS

This section attempts to derive simplified kinetic models for the main reactions expected in the Cleanker pilot plant (formation of belite, calcination and carbonation) using the data available from the TG experiments. A first section 4.1 is devoted to the modelling of Belite formation in Vernasca. Then, calcination and carbonation results have been fitted to different particle submodels (sections 4.2 and 4.3 respectively) in order to derive the kinetic parameters.

4.1 Rates of Belite formation in Vernasca

In view of the results included in section 3.2, and following early investigation in the CEMCAP project, the 3D-Diffusion model proposed by Jander and Hoffmann (1934) has been used to estimate the kinetics of the two reactions that lead to belite formation:

$$X_{Bb} = 1 - \left[1 - (k_{Bb}t)^{1/2}\right]^3 \quad [5.1]$$

$$X_{Ba} = 1 - \left[1 - (k_{Ba}t)^{1/2}\right]^3 \quad [5.2]$$

where the parameter k_{Bb} and k_{Ba} are the reaction rate coefficients which are assumed to have an Arrhenius dependency with temperature.

The experimental data from the non-isothermal tests have been used to calculate the reaction rate coefficient and the activation energy corresponding to the reaction of CaCO_3 with SiO_2 (k_{Bb}). Values of 6.64 s^{-1} and 133 kJ/mol have been determined, respectively, for the experimental conditions tested in the TG.

Figure 4.1 represents the comparison between the experimental conversion of CaCO_3 to belite and the calculated values from the model. As can be seen, the kinetic model gives a reasonable prediction of the belite formation for low conversions while a poorer agreement is found at higher conversions. As it is unlikely to form significant amount of belite from CaCO_3 under typical calcination conditions in CaL calciners, this model is still useful to interpret experimental results from TGA studies and to predict the formation of belite from CaCO_3 in CaL processes.

Figure 4.1. Comparison between experimental conversions of CaCO_3 to belite and calculated conversions using the Jander's model.

The most relevant kinetic information regarding belite formation corresponds to the reaction of CaO and SiO_2 (reaction 2.2). Figure 4.2 represents the evolution of X_{Ba} with time for Vernasca raw meal (left) and for the reference marl Bilbao (right).

Figure 4.2. Evolution of CaO conversion to Belite with time at different temperatures: Vernasca (left), Bilbao (right) The solid lines correspond to model predictions.

As can be seen, the proposed model describes accurately the evolution of the formation of belite from CaO in the samples of Bilbao (marl) even for reaction times up to 80 min and conversion of 0.6. However, in the case of Vernasca raw meal, the model tends to overestimate the formation of belite, especially for periods of time longer than 25 min. This can be due to the fact that Vernasca is a mixture of a limestone and a marl and, therefore, the aggregation of the Ca and Si compounds is lower than in the case of Bilbao.

A particular series of experiments at 895 °C were conducted with Marine (i.e. the marl component of Vernasca) to include an additional marl for comparison purposes. As can be seen in Figure 4.3 left, the belite formation rate at 895 °C for Vernasca is significantly lower than the values obtained for Marine and Bilbao, which present a similar trend. This result supports the assumption that the different behavior of Vernasca raw meal is mainly due its different aggregation level.

Figure 4.3 right shows the Arrhenius dependence of the belite formation rate from CaO obtained for Bilbao between 815 and 890 °C (dots in black). This graph also shows the data reported by Weisweiler and Osen (1988) for the same reaction with mixtures of CaO and SiO₂ but obtained at higher temperatures (from 1000 °C to 1400 °C) (red dots). Despite the great difference of operating conditions used in this study, very similar activation energies were obtained when comparing both series of data (336 kJ/mol for Bilbao and 325 kJ/mol for the other material).

Figure 4.3. Experimental conversions of CaO to Belite for Marine, Vernasca and Bilbao at 895 °C (left). Arrhenius dependency for CaO/SiO₂ mixture (1000-1400 °C) obtained by Weisweiler and Osen (1988) and for Bilbao (815-890 °C).

A preliminary kinetics for Vernasca has been fitted by using the same activation energy of Bilbao (i.e. 336 kJ/mol) with only the pre-exponential factor as fitting parameter, obtaining a value of $4.35 \cdot 10^{10} \text{s}^{-1}$. Thus, it is possible to predict the evolution of X_{Ba} for Vernasca raw meal for different experimental conditions including very short reaction periods times as those expected in the calciner of the cement plant. Figure 4.4 shows the evolution of the theoretical conversion of CaO to belite at temperatures between 870 °C and 950 °C for a time scale up to 50 seconds. As can be observed in the figure, the extent of belite formation greatly increases at higher temperatures. Thus, after 50 seconds a value of X_{Ba} of 0.07 is achieved for a temperature of 870 °C, while a conversion of 0.27 is reached for the same period of time at 950 °C.

Figure 4.4. Theoretical evolution of CaO conversion to belite in Vernasca raw meal at temperatures between 870 °C to 950 °C.

4.2 Rates of calcination of Vernasca raw meal

In the absence of detailed calcination models for raw meals under realistic calcination conditions and gas-solid contact times in the calciner of the CLEANKER CaL process, the scope of this section has been limited to a fitting exercise of available TG calcination rate data presented in section 3.3. For this purpose, a general grain model (Szekely, 1970) has been adapted. This model can be expressed as:

$$X_{calc} = 1 - (1 - k_{calc}f(CO_2)t)^3 \quad [5.3]$$

where X_{calc} is defined here as the conversion of $CaCO_3$ to CaO , k_{calc} has an Arrhenius dependency with temperature and $f(CO_2)$ is a function that takes into account the dependency of CO_2 concentration on the reaction rate. Several expressions are proposed in the literature for accounting this dependency. After testing several expressions, the equation that best fits the experimental data obtained in the TG is the following expression (Khinast et al. 1996):

$$f(CO_2) = \exp\left(-a \frac{P_{CO_2}}{P_{eq}}\right) \quad [5.4]$$

where P_{CO_2} and P_{eq} are the CO_2 partial pressure during calcination and P_{eq} is the equilibrium CO_2 partial pressure at the calcination temperature, respectively. The latter can be calculated as:

$$P_{eq} = 4.137 \times 10^7 \exp\left(-\frac{20474}{T}\right) \quad [5.5]$$

Figure 4.5. Dependency of the calcination kinetics with CO_2 concentration (left). Variation of the kinetic calcination constant with the temperature (Arrhenius dependency) (right).

The parameter a was calculated by fitting the experimental data of Vernasca, obtaining a value of 6.26 (see Figure 4.5 left). Taking into account the variation of the kinetic calcination constant with the temperature (see Figure 4.5 right), an activation

energy of 85 kJ/mol was calculated, which is slightly lower than the typical range of activation energies reported in the literature for different limestones (between 92 and 210 kJ/mol). It was also possible to estimate a pre-exponential factor for Vernasca of 667 s^{-1} .

As example of the results that can yield the simplified models presented in this deliverable, Figure 4.6 presents the theoretical evolution of the conversion of Vernasca during calcination evaluated for two operating conditions: mild calcination carried out with air at 860 °C and harsh calcination carried out with 80 vol.% of CO_2 in the gas phase at 970 °C. During the mild calcination, almost the complete conversion of CaCO_3 can be achieved after 25 seconds. At that time, the molar fraction of CaO deactivated by belite formation is 0.09 and the molar fraction of free CaO is 0.90. During the calcination at harsh conditions, around 50 seconds are required to approach total conversion of CaCO_3 (the high CO_2 content hampers the calcination despite the high operating temperature). Meanwhile, the molar fraction of CaO deactivated by belite formation increased to 0.42 and the free CaO molar fraction decreased to 0.55 (which means a maximum CO_2 carrying capacity of 0.39). It should be noted that there was no free CaO below 3 seconds as the calcination rate is slower than the formation of belite during this short period.

Figure 4.6. Evolution during calcination of theoretical molar fractions of CaCO_3 , CaO into Belite ($x \text{ CaOb}$) and free CaO ($x \text{ CaOf}$) assuming the kinetic models and parameters estimated. Calcination at 860 °C in air (left). Calcination at 970 °C with 80 %vol. of CO_2 .

It is necessary to point out that the calcination kinetic model obtained by fitting of the experimental data obtained in the TGA predicts calcination rates of one order of magnitude lower than the kinetics obtained from the experiments carried out in the drop tube (presented in section 5) and other calcination rates for limestones in a disperse flow (Borgwardt, 1985). This discrepancy could indicate that the TGA would be unable to determine very fast reaction rates, as the calcination of CaCO_3 , although further investigation is needed to elucidate this affirmation.

Regarding the performance of calcined Vernasca raw meal as CO₂ sorbent, it is possible to predict the decay of the maximum carrying capacity with the number of carbonation/calcination cycles assuming that fraction of “free” CaO behaves as the CaO of a limestone. Figure 4.7 right illustrates the calculated decay curve for the sorbent derived from Vernasca raw meal at temperatures between 870 and 950 °C assuming a calcination stage of 50 s. As expected, the loss of CO₂ carrying capacity is promoted at higher temperatures. After 10 cycles, a maximum CO₂ carrying capacity of the sorbent of around 0.17 is calculated for a for calcination temperature of 870 °C. However, when calcining at 950 °C, the maximum conversion decreases up to a residual value of 0.09. These results highlight the need to reduce the calcination temperature and the reaction times as much as possible in order to minimize the drop in CO₂ carrying capacities due to belite formation.

Figure 4.7. Predicted decay CO₂ carrying capacity curves of Vernasca assuming 50 seconds of calcination time at temperatures between 870 °C and 950 °C.

In order to illustrate the potential negative effect of the calcination conditions on the performance of the Vernasca raw meal, a sample supply by Buzzi´s cement plant taken from the pre-calciner was tested in the TGA to determine the CO₂ carrying capacity. As can be seen in Figure 4.8 left, an extremely low CO₂ carrying capacity was observed (around 0.2) for the fresh calcined raw meal. Additional XRD analyses of these samples (Figure 4.8 right) confirmed the presence of several Ca-Si compounds (Ca₂SiO₄, Ca₃SiO₅ and Ca₃Si₂O₇) formed during the calcination in the cement plant which explains the significant reduction of free CaO able to carbonate in the presence of CO₂.

Figure 4.8. Evolution of the CO₂ carrying capacity of a calcined sample from Buzzi's plant (left). XRD spectre of this sample (right).

4.3 Rates of carbonation of free CaO

Finally, the kinetic parameters required to estimate the carbonation rate of free CaO were obtained using the experimental data described in Section 3.4. The carbonation reaction under the kinetic regime was described as a first-order reaction assuming a grain-model reaction (Grasa et. al, 2008). The carbonation conversion at isothermal conditions was calculated as follows:

$$X_{carb} = 1 - (1 - k_{carb}(v_{CO_2} - v_{eq}))t^3 \quad [5.5]$$

where k_{carb} is the carbonation constant rate, v_{CO_2} is the CO₂ molar fraction during the test and v_{eq} is the equilibrium molar fraction of CO₂ at reaction temperature. Figure 4.8 left shows the first-order of reaction when the apparent kinetic constant ($k_{carb}(v_{CO_2} - v_{eq})$) is plotted against $(v_{CO_2} - v_{eq})$ for tests carried out at the same temperature and different CO₂ concentrations. An activation energy of 26 kJ/mol and a pre-exponential factor of 4.51 s⁻¹ were obtained assuming Arrhenius dependency of the carbonation kinetics with the temperature (see Figure 4.8 right).

Figure 4.8. Apparent kinetic constant vs CO_2 concentration (left). Arrhenius dependency of the kinetic carbonation constant with the temperature (right).

These kinetic parameters are in close agreement with the values typically reported in the literature for the carbonation of limes (i.e. activation energies in the range of 20 kJ/mol and 29 kJ/mol) (Grasa et al 2009; Sun et al 2008).

5. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS FROM DROP TUBE EXPERIMENTS

5.1 Characterization of residence times in the drop tube furnace

An analysis of the gas flow pattern was carried out in order to accurately estimate the gas-solid contact times in the drop tube reactor and facilitate the interpretation of the experimental results. Since the solids fed have fine particle size and terminal velocities (0.05 m/s) much lower than the circulating velocity of the gas (0.82 - 2.09 m/s), the velocity of the solids through the reactor should be given by the gas velocity. Residence time distribution (RTD) tests were conducted to characterize deviations from the plug flow for the gas in the form of axial dispersion coefficients. These tests were performed by injecting CO_2 as step tracer at the reactor inlet and measuring the CO_2 concentration change (from 12 to 0% $_v$) at the reactor outlet by means of the CO_2 sensor. The total gas flow injected was around 2.7 m^3/h (i.e., a gas velocity of 0.6 m/s) and the drop tube temperature was kept constant at about 770 °C.

The extent of the axial dispersion in the drop tube, which is given by the dispersion number (D/uL), is derived from the differential mass balance without any chemical reaction represented by Equation [4.1], where t_r is the residence time of the gas, u is the gas velocity and D is the dispersion coefficient (Levenspiel, 1999).

$$t_r \frac{\partial C_A}{\partial t} = \frac{D}{uL} \frac{\partial^2 C_A}{\partial z^2} - \frac{\partial C_A}{\partial z} \quad [4.1]$$

The variance (σ), which is obtained from the E(t) curve (concentration variation with time), is related to the dispersion number by means of Eq. [4.2] (in closed vessels) (Laan, 1958).

$$\sigma_{\theta}^2 = \frac{\sigma^2}{t_r^2} = 2 \frac{D}{uL} - 2 \left(\frac{D}{uL} \right)^2 \left(1 - e^{-uL/D} \right) \quad [4.2]$$

Equations [4.1] and [4.2] need to be applied not only to the reactor but also to the gas conducts taking gas samples to the measuring cells in the CO₂ sensor. The variance of a system composed of several vessels connected in series (i.e., reactor/sensor line+sensor) with low dispersion number (i.e., $D/uL < 0.01$) can be obtained from the sum of the variances of each individual component (Levenspiel, 1999). Therefore, the variance of the drop tube reactor can be derived from Eq. [4.3]:

$$\sigma_{\text{reactor}}^2 = \sigma_{\text{reactor+sensor line+sensor}}^2 - \sigma_{\text{analyser line+sensor}}^2 \quad [4.3]$$

The dispersion number of the complete system (System I) was estimated by injecting a step tracer at the gas secondary injection (see Figure 2.1). The variation of the concentration of CO₂ at the reactor exit was recorded by the sensor and the dispersion number was calculated by means of Eq. [4.2]. Following the same methodology, the dispersion only caused by the sensor and the pipeline that connects the reactor and the sensor (System II) was obtained. In this case, a sudden change in the CO₂ concentration was made by means of a switching valve system connected to the gas sampling point.

Figure 4.1 shows the experimental and theoretical F(t) curves (dimensionless output to a step input) obtained for systems I and II. A dispersion number (D/uL) for the reactor of 0.017 was calculated from these experimental results, which means a moderate dispersion, and a dispersion coefficient (D) of 0.05 m²/s for the RTD tests conditions was obtained. These values are in agreement to those attained by using the correlation developed by Levenspiel (1958) to describe the dispersion of fluids through pipes (i.e., $D/uL=0.012$, $D=0.04$ m²/s).

Figure 4.1. Experimental and theoretical $F(t)$ curves obtained during the step tracer tests (System I is composed of reactor, pipeline downstream and sensor; System II is composed of a tube without dispersion, the pipeline downstream and sensor) .

Fig. 4.2 shows the predicted $F(t)$ curve obtained after a step input in the drop tube with a dispersion number (D/uL) of 0.017 and the resulting C curve (dF/dt vs. the normalized residence time, θ), which represents the expected spread of the outlet signal after a pulse inlet. As can be seen, there is a little discrepancy between the real residence time of the gas and the value obtained directly from the gas velocity and the reactor length ($t_{r,real} = 0.95 t_{r,calculated}$), due to the moderate dispersion existing in the reactor. This result has been taken into account when interpreting the experimental data.

Figure 4.2. Predicted spread of the F curve in the reactor for a step input (left); predicted spread of the C curve in the reactor for a pulse input (right).

5.2 Calcination experiments with Vernasca

All the calcination tests were conducted following the same experimental procedure. Before the reaction experiments, the drop tube reactor is progressively heated up the desired calcination temperature is achieved. Heat is supplied by the heating elements distributed along the reactor and by air fed at the top of the drop tube at very high temperature after having passed through the electric gas preheater. An example of the heating up of the drop tube is represented in Figure 4.3 left. Typically, around 4 hours are needed to increase the temperature of the reactor from ambient conditions up to the targeted temperature profile.

The maximum temperature was achieved in the first half of the reactor thanks to the sensible heat of the inlet gas that arrives at temperatures higher than 900 °C. However, the temperature presents a decreased profile from top to bottom due to heat losses. In fact, it was not possible to achieve temperatures around to 900°C at steady conditions by means of the gas preheater and the heating elements. Then, pulverized coal is mixed with Vernasca raw meal (between 15 and 25%wt. of the total solids) to supply the surplus of heat needed for those experiments carried out at temperatures higher than 850 °C.

Figure 4.3. right shows a typical temperature profile during a calcination test with co-feeding of coal. The zone between the dot lines displayed in the figure corresponds to the period of time during which the solids (raw meal+coal) were fed into the drop tube reactor.

Figure 4.3. Example of drop tube preheating before a calcination test (left) and an example of temperature profiles during a calcination test (distances referred from the solids injection point) (right).

As can be seen in this graph, a relatively uniform profile along the reactor length can be achieved with ranging temperatures between 850 and 880 °C. The increase in temperature observed in the upper part of the tube is caused by the combustion of coal. A significant temperature drop is systematically measured at around 0.65 m from the solids injection point. This corresponds to the part of the drop tube attached to the

supporting structure, where a substantial heat loss is unavoidable (although partially compensated by internal coal combustion). The temperature registered at 5.15 m from the solids injection point is significantly lower ($<780^{\circ}\text{C}$) respect to the average value mainly due to the increased heat losses at the exit of the reactor. In order to simplify the interpretation of the results, this part of the tube is not considered as reaction zone. As the experiments were carried out with very low flow of solids, an accurate measure of very small variations of the CO_2 concentration in the gas phase is required. Two gas analysers and two CO_2 sensors were distributed along the drop tube reactor to ensure reliable gas composition measurements. As explained in section 2.2, there is a solid sampling device located at the exit of the drop tube reactor. Therefore, the extent of the calcination reaction can be followed not only by the measurement of the CO_2 concentration in the gas phase, but also by the chemical analysis of the solid particles collected. This is a more reliable determination of the calcination conversion and allows verifying the methodology based on the gas phase analysis.

A typical experiment of calcination can be seen in Figure 4.4., where $\text{CO}_{2,\text{in}}$ corresponds to the CO_2 concentration of gas fed into the reactor and $\text{CO}_{2,\text{out}}$ corresponds to the experimental concentration measured using the two analysers installed in two specific gas sampling points of the drop tube (at 2.65 m and 4.65 m from the injection point, respectively).

Period	Time	Description
1	19:58	Feeding the preheated mixture into the reactor
2	20:01	Injection of the carrier air into the reactor
3	20:06	Feeding of solids
4	20:15	Stopping the feeding of solids
5	20:19	Stopping the carrier air

Figure 4.4. Example of a typical experiment of calcination (average reactor temperature= 850°C , gas velocity= 1.9 m/s , solids flowrate= 0.5 kg/h , inlet CO_2 volume fraction= 0.205).

Calcination tests start by feeding the pre-heated mixture of air and CO₂ into the reactor (Period 1). The mass flow rates of air and CO₂ fed into the reactor are verified by the gas composition measured by the gas analysers. In absence of reaction, the concentration of CO₂ at the reactor inlet and throughout the drop tube should be the same. In Period 2, the carrier air is fed into the reactor diluting the CO₂ content. The flow rate of carrier air is then validated with the measurements observed in the gas analysers. Once ensuring the experimental conditions along the reactor are stable, the solid feeding system is turned on and the particles are injected into the drop tube reactor (Period 3). The concentration of CO₂ rapidly increases due to the calcination of the raw meal (and due to the combustion when coal is also fed into). After a short transition period, the CO₂ concentration reaches a relatively stable value. After some minutes (around 10 min in this example), the feeding of solids is stopped and at that point (Period 4), the CO₂ concentration decreases until it reaches the initial value, verifying that no problems have occurred. Finally, the carrier air is stopped (Period 5) and the measure of the CO₂ concentration should validate the stability of the inlet gas flowrate.

The main operation variables tested in the drop tube during the experiments of calcination are summarized in Table 4.1. As can be seen, the experiments have been carried out in a wide range of temperatures, gas velocities and inlet CO₂ volume fractions in order to cover a wide range of experimental conditions. This has allowed obtaining sufficient information to estimate the kinetics for the calcination of Vernasca raw meal in very short gas/solid contact times.

Table 4.1 Main operation conditions tested during the calcination tests in the drop tube.

Calciner temperature (°C)	T_{calc}	790-935
Calciner inlet velocity (m/s)	u_{calc}	0.8-2.1
Inlet CO ₂ volume fraction to the calciner	V_{CO_2}	0.00-0.73
Solids flowrate (kg/h)		0.28-0.59

Figures 4.5 and 4.6 present a summary of the main results obtained during the experimental campaigns in the drop tube reactor. In general, the trends observed during these test are in agreement with previous studies of calcination kinetics carried out under similar conditions of temperature and partial pressure of CO₂ (Khinast et al. (1996), Borgwardt (1985), Garcia Labiano et al. (2002), Rao (1996), Hu and Scaroni (1996), Martinez et al. (2012)). Figure 4.5 shows the effect of the temperature on the calcination conversion of Vernasca raw meal under a reaction atmosphere with 20% vol. of CO₂. Two different symbols are used to differentiate the experiments carried out with and without coal. As expected, the calcination temperature has a strong effect on X_{calc} . Thus, temperatures close to 900 °C promotes the calcination reaction and a X_{calc} of around 0.80 is achieved for a residence time of 2.2 s. However, the calcination conversion at 820 °C for the same reaction time is only 0.4.

Figure 4.5. Increment of the calcination conversion under a reaction atmosphere with 20%_v CO₂ for temperatures between 820 and 895°C. Solid lines correspond to model predictions (solid line-Kinast model, dashed line-Martínez model).

Figure 4.6 shows the evolution of the calcination conversion of Vernasca raw meal under different CO₂ concentrations (from 0 to 80%) and reaction temperatures (from 820 to 895°C). It is important to note that several calcination experiments at 850°C of average temperature in the presence of air were carried out by feeding pure raw meal and a mixture of Vernasca and coal. As can be seen in the corresponding figure, similar calcination conversions were achieved in these tests (between 0.82 and 0.88 for a residence time of 2.5-3 s), which demonstrates that the combustion of coal in situ does not affect the extent of the calcination reaction. Increasing the contents of CO₂ in the feed hindered the calcination conversion for the different temperatures tested due to equilibrium restrictions. However, it must be highlighted that high calcination conversions can be achieved under high CO₂ concentrations even at short reaction times. Thus, a X_{calc} of 0.63 was achieved in less than 4 s under 70%_v CO₂ at 895 °C.

Figure 4.6. Evolution of the calcination conversion with the CO₂ concentration in the inlet gas at (a) 820 °C, (b) 850 °C, (c) 875 °C and (d) 895 °C. Solid lines correspond to model predictions (solid line-Kinast model, dashed line-Martínez model).

From the experimental information obtained in each test, the following CO₂ mass balance, based on the gas phase, can be solved:

$$\left(\text{Total } CO_2 \text{ formed in the gas phase} \right) - \left(CO_2 \text{ formed by coal combustion} \right) = \left(CaO \text{ formed from } CaCO_3 \text{ calcination} \right) \quad [4.4]$$

or:

$$\left(F_{CO_2out} - F_{CO_2in} \right) - F_{CO_2,combustion} = F_{CaCO_3in} X_{calc} \quad [4.5]$$

where the molar flow rates of CO₂ at the inlet and outlet of the drop tube, F_{CO_2in} and F_{CO_2out} respectively, can be determined from the air and CO₂ flows fed into the reactor and from the measurement of the composition of the gas phase leaving the reactor. The molar flow of CaCO₃ (F_{CaCO_3in}) is obtained by the mass flow of solids fed during the experiment. The molar flow of CO₂ formed by the coal combustion (when relevant) is calculated by a mass balance to the O₂:

$$\left(CO_2 \text{ formed by coal combustion} \right) = \left(O_2 \text{ removed from the gas phase} \right) \quad [4.6]$$

or

$$F_{CO_2,combustion} = F_{O_2in} - F_{O_2out} \quad [4.7]$$

F_{O_2in} and F_{O_2out} are the molar flow rates of O_2 at the inlet and at different points throughout the drop tube, respectively, and they can be obtained from the inlet air molar flow and from the analysis of the gas composition at different measure points. Then, the extent of the calcination reaction (X_{calc}) of the raw meal can be calculated as follows:

$$X_{calc} = \frac{F_{CO_2out} - F_{CO_2in} - F_{CO_2,combustion}}{F_{CaCO_3in}} \quad [4.8]$$

As previously explained above, it is also possible to calculate the extent of the calcination from the solids taken during each test in order to validate the soundness of experimental information:

$$X_{calc} = \frac{X_{CaCO_3in} - X_{CaCO_3out}}{X_{CaCO_3in}} \quad [4.8]$$

A preliminary analysis of the results obtained in the drop tube reactor is presented in this report and a more elaborate study will be carried out and presented in the next deliverable 5.2. For this purpose, a kinetic model derived from the classic grain model reported by Szekely and Evans (1970) has been used to describe the calcination reaction:

$$\left(\frac{dX_{calc}}{dt}\right)_{reactor} = k'(1 - X_{calc})^{2/3} \quad [4.12]$$

Two different expressions have been tested in this preliminary analysis for the apparent kinetic constant, k' . The first model is defined according to that proposed by Khinast et al. (1996) as follows:

$$k' = k_c e^{\left(-a \frac{\overline{v_{CO_2}}}{v_{CO_2,eq}}\right)} \quad [4.13]$$

where the parameter k_c is the kinetic constant, $\overline{v_{CO_2}}$ the mean CO_2 volume fraction, $v_{CO_2,eq}$ the volume fraction of CO_2 in the equilibrium and a a fitting parameter independent of the reaction temperature. Equation [4.12] can be integrated and combined with Equation [4.13] to estimate the calcination conversion with the reaction time according to:

$$X_{calc} = 1 - \left(1 - \frac{k' t_r}{3}\right)^3 = 1 - \left(1 - \frac{k_c e^{\left(-a \frac{\overline{v_{CO_2}}}{v_{CO_2,eq}}\right)} t_r}{3}\right)^3 \quad [4.14]$$

By combining equation [4.14] with the CO₂ mass balance (equation [4.8]), the following expression is obtained:

$$\frac{F_{CO2out} - F_{CO2in} - F_{CO2,combustion}}{F_{CaCO3in}} = 1 - \left(1 - \frac{k_c e^{\left(-a \frac{\overline{v_{CO2}}}{v_{CO2,eq}}\right) t_r}}{3} \right)^3 \quad [4.15]$$

The kinetic constant, k_c , varies with the temperature following the Arrhenius equation:

$$k_c = k_{c0} e^{\left(-\frac{E_a}{RT}\right)} \quad [4.16]$$

where k_{c0} is the pre-exponential factor, R the ideal gas constant and E_a the activation energy. Using the experimental data obtained in the drop tube reactor, k_c and a have been calculated as fitting parameters by comparing both terms of equation [4.15].

The second model is based on that proposed by Martínez et al. (2012) in which the apparent kinetic constant, k' , is defined as follows:

$$k' = k_{cM} (v_{CO2,eq} - \overline{v_{CO2}}) \quad [4.16]$$

where k_{cM} is the kinetic constant assumed by Martínez et al. (2012). The relation between the calcination conversion of the raw meal and the reaction time can be attained from integrating equation [4.12] and using the expression of equation [4.16] for k' :

$$X_{calc} = 1 - \left(1 - \frac{k_{cM} (v_{CO2,eq} - \overline{v_{CO2}}) t_r}{3} \right)^3 \quad [4.17]$$

By combining equation [4.17] with the CO₂ mass balance (equation [4.8]), the following expression can be derived:

$$\frac{F_{CO2out} - F_{CO2in} - F_{CO2,combustion}}{F_{CaCO3in}} = 1 - \left(1 - \frac{k_{cM} (v_{CO2,eq} - \overline{v_{CO2}}) t_r}{3} \right)^3 \quad [4.18]$$

The kinetic constant k_{cM} can be then calculated as a fitting parameter by comparing both terms of equation [4.18].

As indicated, the kinetic constants, k_c and k_{cM} , has been calculated as fitting parameters using Eqs. 4.15 and 4.18 and the experimental information obtained in the drop tube reactor. In order to adjust the model bases on Kinast approach, the parameter a has also been calculated as a fitting parameter assuming that it is constant for the different temperatures tested. The calculated evolution of the calcination conversion with time obtained with both models is presented in Figures 4.5 and 4.6 (solid line-Kinast, dashed line-Martínez).

Table 4.2. Variation of the kinetic constant, k_c and k_{cM} , with the reaction temperature.

Temperature (°C)	k_c (s ⁻¹)	k_{cM} (s ⁻¹)
820	0.42	1.30
850	0.59	1.33
875	0.79	1.12
895	1.09	1.34

The parameter a was found to be 1.38. Then, the kinetic constants have been used to derive the activation energy and the pre-exponential factors for each model. In the case of the first model based on Kinast et al approach (1996), values of $k_0=870893$ s⁻¹ and $E_a=133$ kJ/mol have been found. This value of the activation energy is within the range of between 110 and 210 kJ/mol reported in the literature (Borgwardt (1985), Dennis and Hayhurst (1978), Garcia Labiano et al. (2002), Rao (1996)). However, in this case of the second model based on Martinez approach (2012), the calculated values of the kinetic constant k_{cM} are very similar within the range of temperatures tested. This is an unexpected result that would require a more elaborated analysis that will be present in deliverable 5.2.

Finally, Figure 4.7 illustrates the comparison between the experimental calcination conversions obtained in the tests and the calculated values using both models. As can be seen, there is a reasonable agreement between the experimental and the calculated values using both models. A better regression coefficient (r^2) is obtained with the kinetic model proposed by Khinast el al. ((1996) (0.73 vs 0.60).

Figure 4.7. Comparison between the experimental increment of calcination conversion and the calculated values assuming the kinetic model reported by Martinez et al. (2012), equation [4.17].

The calcination kinetics calculated in the drop tube reactor are an order of magnitude faster than those derived from the TG test. According to the workplan for WP5, future experimental and modelling work with other materials and raw meals, at relevant calcination conditions and reaction times, should improve the understanding of the results described in this deliverable. However, the information reported here for Vernasca raw meal should be taken into account in the design and operation strategies of the Cleanker pilot.

6. CONCLUSIONS

Tests have been carried out with samples of Vernasca raw meal aiming to quantify the kinetic rates of calcination and carbonation under conditions as close as possible to those expected in the Cleanker Calcium Looping pilot. This raw meal is a mixture of a high purity limestone and marl. Compared to natural limestones, the calcined raw meal presented a complex behavior as sorbent. This was mainly due to the formation of belite (Ca_2SiO_4), which reduces the amount of CaO available to react with CO_2 . Thus, the formation of belite through the reaction of SiO_2 with CaCO_3 and CaO has been studied by means of TG analysis and simplified models have been tuned to the experimental results to obtain kinetic parameters. Activation energies of 133 and 336 kJ/mol have been obtained, respectively, which are consistent with the data available in the literature. These simplified models allow calculating the fraction of CaO available to react with CO_2 and therefore to estimate the carrying capacity of the sorbent with the number of cycles. The preliminary results presented in this report have confirmed the high activity and CO_2 carrying capacity of the calcined raw meal of Vernasca when calcination is sufficiently fast to minimise reactions of CaO with other solid species in the marl component of the raw meal.

Carbonation tests of calcined raw meal carried out in TG have indicated that the fraction of active CaO in the sorbent presents a similar behaviour than those derived from natural limestones. Thus, an activation energy of 26 kJ/mol and a pre-exponential factor of 4.51 s^{-1} have been obtained by the fitting of the experimental results to a standard grain model. Regarding the calcination studies of Vernasca raw meal, two different devices have been used, a TG analyser and a drop tube furnace. The preliminary tests showed that calcination kinetics can be an order of magnitude faster in the drop tube than those obtained in the TGA. Thus, calcination conversions up to 0.6 have been achieved under CO_2 molar fractions of 0.7 at 895 °C in less than 4 s. The estimation of calcination reaction rates are still subjected to great uncertainty, especially if they are obtained only from TGA, since significant undesired effects could be present in the TG reaction environment. The experimental results available so far have been fitted to a standard grain model in order to derive the kinetic parameters. An activation energy of 133 kJ/mol has been obtained for the data obtained in the drop tube reactor, which is in agreement with data available in the literature.

Experimental and modelling work with other materials and raw meals, at relevant calcination and carbonation conditions and reaction times, is expected to be carried out in the next reporting period, in order to improve the understanding of the results described

in this deliverable. However, the information reported here for Vernasca raw meal should be taken into account in the design and operation strategies of the Cleanker pilot.

NOMENCLATURE

E_a	Activation energy
F_i	Molar flow rate of i
k_{CO}	Arrhenius exponential factor
k_c, k', k_M	Kinetic constant
R	Ideal gas constant
RTD	Residence time distribution
TGA	Thermogravimetric analyzer
t_r	Residence time
X	Molar conversion of free CaO to CaCO ₃
X_{Ba}	Molar conversion of CaO to Ca ₂ SiO ₄
X_{Bb}	Molar conversion of CaCO ₃ to Ca ₂ SiO ₄
X_{calc}	Molar conversion of CaCO ₃ to CaO
X_N	Maximum conversion of CaO to CaCO ₃ in cycle N
\overline{v}_{CO_2}	Mean CO ₂ volume fraction,
$v_{CO_2,eq}$	Volume fraction of CO ₂ in the equilibrium

REFERENCES

- CEMCAP, 2017. D12.2: Results of entrained flow carbonator/calcliner tests. www.sintef.no/projectweb/cemcap/results/.
- Alonso, M.; Criado, Y. A.; Abanades, J. C.; Grasa, G., Undesired effects in the determination of CO₂ carrying capacities of CaO during TG testing. *Fuel* **2014**, 127, 52-61.
- Alonso, M.; Álvarez Criado, Y.; Fernández, J. R.; Abanades, C., CO₂ Carrying Capacities of Cement Raw Meals in Calcium Looping Systems. *Energy Fuels* **2017**, 31, (12), 13955-13962.
- Borgwardt, R. H., Calcination kinetics and surface-area of dispersed limestone particles. *AIChE J.* **1985**, 31, (1), 103-111. Dennis, J.S., Hayhurst A.N. The effect of CO₂ on the kinetics and extent of calcination of limestone and dolomite particles in fluidised beds. *Chem. Eng. Sci.* **1987**, 42(10), 2361-2372.
- García-Labiano, F., et al. Calcination of calcium-based sorbents at pressure in a broad range of CO₂ concentrations. *Chem. Eng. Sci.* **2002**, 57(13), 2381-2393.
- Grasa, G. S.; Abanades, J. C., CO₂ capture capacity of CaO in long series of carbonation/calcination cycles. *Ind. Eng. Chem. Res.* **2006**, 45, (26), 8846-8851.
- Grasa, G. S.; Abanades, J. C.; Alonso, M.; Gonzalez, B., Reactivity of highly cycled particles of CaO in a carbonation/calcination loop. *Chem. Eng. J.* **2008**, 137, (3), 561-567.
- Grasa, G.; Murillo, R.; Alonso, M.; Abanades, J. C., Application of the Random Pore Model to the Carbonation Cyclic Reaction. *AIChE J.* **2009**, 55, (5), 1246-1255.
- Hu, N., Scaroni A.W. Calcination of pulverized limestone particles under furnace injection conditions. *Fuel* **1996**, 75(2), 177-186.
- Jander, W.; Hoffmann, E., Reaktionen im festen Zustande bei höheren Temperaturen. XI. Mitteilung. Die Reaktion zwischen Calciumoxyd und Siliciumdioxyd. *Zeitschrift für anorganische und allgemeine Chemie* 1934, 218, 211-223.
- Khinast, J.; Krammer, G. F.; Brunner, C.; Staudinger, G., Decomposition of limestone: The influence of CO₂ and particle size on the reaction rate. *Chem. Eng. Sci.* **1996**, 51, (4), 623-634.
- Laan, v.d., Letters to the editors. *Chem. Eng. Sci.* **1958**, 7(3), 187-191.
- Levenspiel, O., *Chemical reaction engineering*. 1999: Wiley.
- Martinez, I.; Grasa, G.; Murillo, R.; Arias, B.; Abanades, J. C., Kinetics of Calcination of Partially Carbonated Particles in a Ca-Looping System for CO₂ Capture. *Energy Fuels* **2012**, 26, (2), 1432-1440
- Rao, T.R., Kinetics of calcium carbonate decomposition. *Chem. Eng. Technol.* **1996**, 19(4), 373-377.

Szekely, J., Evans, J.W. A structural model for gas—solid reactions with a moving boundary. *Chem. Eng. Sci.* **1970**, 25(6), 1091-1107.

Sun, P., Grace, J. R., Lim, C. J., Anthony, E. J., Determination of intrinsic rate constants of the CaO-CO₂ reaction. *Chem. Eng. Sci.* **2008**, 63, (1), 47-56.

Taylor, H. F. W., *Cement Chemistry*. Thomas Telford: London, 1997. Weisweiler, W.; Osen, E. J.; Höfer, H., Kinetic studies in the CaO-SiO₂- system part II reaction rate constants and activation energies of selected diffusion couples. *Cem. Concr. Res.* **1988**, 18, (1), 55-62.

APPENDIX

A.1 Experimental results of calcination

A.1.1 Campaign 1: RTD tests

Residence time distribution tests were carried out in order to study the gas flow behavior and characterize the residence time in the drop tube reactor. The deviations from the gas plug flow were defined by means of the axial dispersion coefficient.

These tests were performed by injecting a step tracer to a known inlet gas flow (no solids were injected) and measuring the rapid CO₂ concentration change by means of the CO₂ sensor. As explained in the section 4.1 of this document, there was necessary to carry out two different kinds of step tracer tests to obtain the axial dispersion coefficient of the reactor: one taking into account the whole system (System I) that includes the reactor, the pipelines that connect it with the sensor and the sensor itself and another one considering only the pipelines and the sensor (System II).

Regarding System I, there were made 10 experiments at the same reactor temperature (around 770°C). Six of them were carried out without injecting the carrier air into the drop tube (total gas flow around 2.5 m³/h), and the other four injecting it (total gas flow around 2.7 m³/h). The results obtained regarding the axial dispersion coefficient were very similar in the two cases.

In respect of System II, there were carried out 12 experiments at the usual operating conditions of the sensor, i.e. gas flow through the pipeline of 2 l/min and at a temperature around 20 °C. The step tracer tests were carried out varying the CO₂ concentration at the beginning of the gas sampling pipeline, from 3, 5 and 8 to 0%v.

Experiment 1
System I

Solid fed	-
T (°C)	773
u_{gas} (m/s)	0.53
%CO ₂ in	12.9
Solid flow (kg/h)	0.0
Total gas flow (m ³ /h)	2.52

Experiment 2
System I

Solid fed	-
T (°C)	773
u_{gas} (m/s)	0.53
%CO ₂ in	12.9
Solid flow (kg/h)	0.0
Total gas flow (m ³ /h)	2.52

Experiment 3
System I

Solid fed	-
T (°C)	773
u_{gas} (m/s)	0.53
%CO ₂ in	12.9
Solid flow (kg/h)	0.0
Total gas flow (m ³ /h)	2.52

Experiment 4
System I

Solid fed	-
T (°C)	773
u_{gas} (m/s)	0.53
%CO ₂ in	12.9
Solid flow (kg/h)	0.0
Total gas flow (m ³ /h)	2.52

Experiment 5
System I

Solid fed	-
T (°C)	773
u_{gas} (m/s)	0.53
%CO ₂ in	12.9
Solid flow (kg/h)	0.0
Total gas flow (m ³ /h)	2.52

Experiment 6
System I

Solid fed	-
T (°C)	773
u_{gas} (m/s)	0.53
%CO ₂ in	12.9
Solid flow (kg/h)	0.0
Total gas flow (m ³ /h)	2.52

Experiment 7
System I

Solid fed	-
T (°C)	769
u_{gas} (m/s)	0.57
%CO ₂ in	11.6
Solid flow (kg/h)	0.0
Total gas flow (m ³ /h)	2.70

Experiment 8
System I

Solid fed	-
T (°C)	769
u_{gas} (m/s)	0.57
%CO ₂ in	11.6
Solid flow (kg/h)	0.0
Total gas flow (m ³ /h)	2.70

Experiment 9
System I

Solid fed	-
T (°C)	769
u_{gas} (m/s)	0.57
%CO ₂ in	11.6
Solid flow (kg/h)	0.0
Total gas flow (m ³ /h)	2.70

Experiment 10
System I

Solid fed	-
T (°C)	769
u_{gas} (m/s)	0.57
%CO ₂ in	11.6
Solid flow (kg/h)	0.0
Total gas flow (m ³ /h)	2.70

Experiment 11
System II

Solid fed	-
T (°C)	20
%CO ₂ in	3.0
Solid flow (kg/h)	0.0
Total gas flow (l/min)	2.00

Experiment 12
System II

Solid fed	-
T (°C)	20
%CO ₂ in	3.0
Solid flow (kg/h)	0.0
Total gas flow (l/min)	2.00

Experiment 13
System II

Solid fed	-
T (°C)	20
%CO ₂ in	3.0
Solid flow (kg/h)	0.0
Total gas flow (l/min)	2.00

Experiment 14
System II

Solid fed	-
T (°C)	20
%CO ₂ in	3.0
Solid flow (kg/h)	0.0
Total gas flow (l/min)	2.00

Experiment 15
System II

Solid fed	-
T (°C)	20
%CO ₂ in	5.4
Solid flow (kg/h)	0.0
Total gas flow (l/min)	2.00

Experiment 16
System II

Solid fed	-
T (°C)	20
%CO ₂ in	5.4
Solid flow (kg/h)	0.0
Total gas flow (l/min)	2.00

Experiment 17
System II

Solid fed	-
T (°C)	20
%CO ₂ in	5.4
Solid flow (kg/h)	0.0
Total gas flow (l/min)	2.00

Experiment 18
System II

Solid fed	-
T (°C)	20
%CO ₂ in	5.4
Solid flow (kg/h)	0.0
Total gas flow (l/min)	2.00

Experiment 19
System II

Solid fed	-
T (°C)	20
%CO ₂ in	8.1
Solid flow (kg/h)	0.0
Total gas flow (l/min)	2.00

Experiment 20
System II

Solid fed	-
T (°C)	20
%CO ₂ in	7.8
Solid flow (kg/h)	0.0
Total gas flow (l/min)	2.00

Experiment 21
System II

Solid fed	-
T (°C)	20
%CO ₂ in	8.0
Solid flow (kg/h)	0.0
Total gas flow (l/min)	2.00

Experiment 22
System II

Solid fed	-
T (°C)	20
%CO ₂ in	7.8
Solid flow (kg/h)	0.0
Total gas flow (l/min)	2.00

Campaign 2: Calcination tests

The experiments of this campaign, carried out in the drop tube described in section 1.1, aim at testing the calcination of Vernasca raw meal under different reaction conditions.

The solid, Vernasca or Vernasca mixed with coal, was injected at the beginning of the upright part of the tube using the solid feeding system described in section 1.1. The inlet gas stream, composed of air and CO₂, was preheated in the electric gas preheater and injected into the drop tube.

The extent of the calcination reaction was followed by the measurement of the CO₂ concentration in the gas phase and by the chemical analysis of the solid particle collected in the solid sampling device located at the exit of the reactor. Since the drop tube is equipped with eleven gas sampling points and there are available four gas analysis devices (two analysers and two sensors), it was possible to measure up to four extents of the calcination reaction at four different reaction lengths (i.e. residence times) in just one experiment.

The gas velocity in these experiments ranged from 0.82 to 2.09 m/s, the inlet CO₂ volume fraction from 0 to 0.73 and the reactor temperature from 790 to 935°C, in order to sweep as many experimental conditions as possible.

Experiment 1

Solid fed	Vernasca
T (°C)	845
u_{gas} (m/s)	1.92
CO ₂ in (vol%)	0.0
Solid flow (kg/h)	0.47
Total gas flow (m ³ /h)	8.47

Experiment 2

Solid fed	Vernasca
T (°C)	855
u_{gas} (m/s)	1.95
CO ₂ in (vol%)	0.0
Solid flow (kg/h)	0.49
Total gas flow (m ³ /h)	8.53

Experiment 3

Solid fed	Vernasca+Cork
T (°C)	853
u_{gas} (m/s)	1.94
CO ₂ in (vol%)	0.0
Solid flow (kg/h)	0.41
Total gas flow (m ³ /h)	8.53

Experiment 4

Solid fed	Vernasca
T (°C)	818
u_{gas} (m/s)	1.89
CO ₂ in (vol%)	0.0
Solid flow (kg/h)	0.38
Total gas flow (m ³ /h)	8.54

Experiment 5

Solid fed	Vernasca+Coal(15%)
T (°C)	858
u_{gas} (m/s)	1.96
CO ₂ in (vol%)	0.0
Solid flow (kg/h)	0.50
Total gas flow (m ³ /h)	8.56

Experiment 6

Solid fed	Vernasca+Coal(25%)
T (°C)	895
u_{gas} (m/s)	2.02
CO ₂ in (vol%)	0.0
Solid flow (kg/h)	0.37
Total gas flow (m ³ /h)	8.56

Experiment 7

Solid fed	Vernasca+Coal(25%)
T (°C)	890
u_{gas} (m/s)	1.83
CO ₂ in (vol%)	46.8
Solid flow (kg/h)	0.44
Total gas flow (m ³ /h)	7.80

Experiment 8

Solid fed	Vernasca+Coal(15%)
T (°C)	870
u_{gas} (m/s)	2.02
CO ₂ in (vol%)	20.4
Solid flow (kg/h)	0.40
Total gas flow (m ³ /h)	8.73

Experiment 9

Solid fed	Vernasca+Coal(15%)
T (°C)	873
u_{gas} (m/s)	1.95
CO ₂ in (vol%)	36.6
Solid flow (kg/h)	0.43
Total gas flow (m ³ /h)	8.41

Experiment 10

Solid fed	Vernasca+Coal(15%)
T (°C)	875
u_{gas} (m/s)	1.96
CO ₂ in (vol%)	30.6
Solid flow (kg/h)	0.42
Total gas flow (m ³ /h)	8.45

Experiment 11

Solid fed	Vernasca+Coal(15%)
T (°C)	833
u_{gas} (m/s)	1.85
CO ₂ in (vol%)	0.0
Solid flow (kg/h)	0.38
Total gas flow (m ³ /h)	8.27

Experiment 12

Solid fed	Vernasca+Coal(15%)
T (°C)	829
u_{gas} (m/s)	1.88
CO ₂ in (vol%)	15.6
Solid flow (kg/h)	0.37
Total gas flow (m ³ /h)	8.41

Experiment 13

Solid fed	Vernasca+Coal(25%)
T (°C)	880
u_{gas} (m/s)	1.95
CO ₂ in (vol%)	0.0
Solid flow (kg/h)	0.36
Total gas flow (m ³ /h)	8.34

Experiment 14

Solid fed	Vernasca+Coal(25%)
T (°C)	877
u_{gas} (m/s)	1.94
CO ₂ in (vol%)	20.9
Solid flow (kg/h)	0.33
Total gas flow (m ³ /h)	8.32

Experiment 15

Solid fed	Vernasca+Coal(25%)
T (°C)	877
u_{gas} (m/s)	1.89
CO ₂ in (vol%)	18.6
Solid flow (kg/h)	0.36
Total gas flow (m ³ /h)	8.12

Experiment 16

Solid fed	Vernasca+Coal(25%)
T (°C)	881
u_{gas} (m/s)	1.71
CO ₂ in (vol%)	53.6
Solid flow (kg/h)	0.34
Total gas flow (m ³ /h)	7.33

Experiment 17

Solid fed	Vernasca+Coal(25%)
T (°C)	872
u_{gas} (m/s)	1.28
CO ₂ in (vol%)	72.6
Solid flow (kg/h)	0.25
Total gas flow (m ³ /h)	5.52

Experiment 18

Solid fed	Vernasca+Coal(25%)
T (°C)	875
u_{gas} (m/s)	2.01
CO ₂ in (vol%)	0.0
Solid flow (kg/h)	0.38
Total gas flow (m ³ /h)	8.63

Experiment 19

Solid fed	Vernasca+Coal(25%)
T (°C)	876
u_{gas} (m/s)	1.87
CO ₂ in (vol%)	20.1
Solid flow (kg/h)	0.35
Total gas flow (m ³ /h)	8.06

Experiment 20

Solid fed	Vernasca+Coal(25%)
T (°C)	877
u_{gas} (m/s)	1.95
CO ₂ in (vol%)	30.4
Solid flow (kg/h)	0.35
Total gas flow (m ³ /h)	8.39

Experiment 21

Solid fed	Vernasca+Coal(25%)
T (°C)	879
u_{gas} (m/s)	1.58
CO ₂ in (vol%)	50.0
Solid flow (kg/h)	0.39
Total gas flow (m ³ /h)	6.80

Experiment 22

Solid fed	Vernasca+Coal(25%)
T (°C)	878
u_{gas} (m/s)	1.36
CO ₂ in (vol%)	69.3
Solid flow (kg/h)	0.32
Total gas flow (m ³ /h)	5.82

Experiment 23

Solid fed	Vernasca
T (°C)	853
u_{gas} (m/s)	1.60
CO ₂ in (vol%)	49.8
Solid flow (kg/h)	0.48
Total gas flow (m ³ /h)	7.02

Experiment 24

Solid fed	Vernasca
T (°C)	850
u_{gas} (m/s)	1.88
CO ₂ in (vol%)	20.5
Solid flow (kg/h)	0.54
Total gas flow (m ³ /h)	8.25

Experiment 25

Solid fed	Vernasca
T (°C)	847
u_{gas} (m/s)	1.54
CO ₂ in (vol%)	0.1
Solid flow (kg/h)	0.56
Total gas flow (m ³ /h)	6.80

Experiment 26

Solid fed	Vernasca
T (°C)	810
u_{gas} (m/s)	1.88
CO ₂ in (vol%)	0.0
Solid flow (kg/h)	0.57
Total gas flow (m ³ /h)	8.58

Experiment 27

Solid fed	Vernasca
T (°C)	822
u_{gas} (m/s)	1.83
CO ₂ in (vol%)	15.6
Solid flow (kg/h)	0.59
Total gas flow (m ³ /h)	8.24

Experiment 28

Solid fed	Vernasca+Coal(15%)
T (°C)	895
u_{gas} (m/s)	0.93
CO ₂ in (vol%)	80.0
Solid flow (kg/h)	0.40
Total gas flow (m ³ /h)	3.99

Experiment 29

Solid fed	Vernasca+Coal(15%)
T (°C)	895
u_{gas} (m/s)	0.82
CO ₂ in (vol%)	77.5
Solid flow (kg/h)	0.48
Total gas flow (m ³ /h)	3.53

